

QUIZ

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied x US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author x did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which treaty led to the establishment of the European Union.¹

- Treaty of Maastricht 1992
- Treaty of Paris 1951
- Treaty of Rome 1957
- The Greenland Treaty 1984

2. What is not a potential problem when choosing words in sentences.²

- Too many nouns.
- Redundancy.

¹ European Commission . *English Style Guide - A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. (Brussels: European Commission - Directorate-General for Translation, 2011), 52.

² Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000*. (Wilmington: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 9.

- Repetition.
- Too many vague words.

3. **Which is not a form of a secondary legislation for the European Union?**³

- Treaty**
- Regulations
- Directives
- Decisions

4. **What is not an element of the four main elements of literature?**⁴

- Idea**
- Setting
- Characterization
- Plot

5. **What is not a step of essay writing ?**⁵

- Copy the essay**
- Writing the essay
- Organizing your ideas

³ European Commission (2011), 56.

⁴ Sebranek et. al. (1999), 176.

⁵ Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1. 2nd ed.* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1-5.

Research the topic

6. **When do you not need to provide a citation?**⁶

When you convey basic common knowledge.

When you quote a text.

When you paraphrase a read text.

When you quote a speech of someone.

7. **What is not a trustworthy source of reference ?**⁷

Word of mouth on facebook

Book

A treaty

Legal texts

8. **Which institution of the European Union comprises the Heads of States?**⁸

European Council

European Parliament

Commission

⁶ Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4. 2nd ed.* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 57.

⁷ Turabian, Kate. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 9th . Edited by Wayne Booth, Gregory Colomb, Joseph Williams, Joseph Bizup, & William FitzGerald. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 28.

⁸ European Commission (2011). 64-65.

Court of Auditors

9. **What is not a common error in research papers?**⁹

Accurately researching the subject.

Incorporating anecdotal information.

Using inaccurate words.

Anthropomorphizing.

10. **What is not a European Financial Institution?**¹⁰

Federal Reserves Bank.

European Central Bank.

European Investment Bank.

European Investment Fund.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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⁹ EUCLID (2020), 8-9.

¹⁰ European Commission (2011), 67-68.

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